

TOPIC CLASSIFICATION OF UZBEK TEXTS

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Abstract. *Topic classification of text is an important task in the field of natural language processing, where the main goal is to classify text data into predefined categories. In this study, we analyze the dataset creation and methods for evaluating multi-tag news series as part of topic-based topic classification. First, in the article, we present obtained corpus for the classification of texts in Uzbek language. This corpus was collected from 5 different news and press websites and contains 4 categories of news, press and legal texts. We also trained a rule-based machine learning model and a neural network model for subject classification in this newly created corpus experiment. Experiments show that models based on recurrent neural network and convolutional neural network outperform rule-based models.*

Keywords: *topic classification, neural networks, Uzbek language, corpora.*

Introduction. Topic classification plays a pivotal role in natural language processing (NLP), aiming to assign text documents to predefined categories. This task is fundamental in numerous practical applications, including sentiment analysis, spam filtering, and topic modeling. Given the vast influx of unstructured data generated every day, topic classification serves as an essential tool for organizing this information, allowing for the extraction of meaningful insights and aiding in decision-making processes. Our study underlines benefit of leveraging both traditional and deep learning models in the case of text classification in low-resource languages like Uzbek. Results clearly show that logistic regression models yield strong performance with the combination of word-level and character-level n-grams and even more so when TF-IDF matrices are concatenated. That would imply that traditional models could still play a significant role in text classification tasks, provided they are properly tuned. While neural network models outperform rule-based models, especially when pre-trained word embeddings are used, this again underlines that the inclusion of language-specific knowledge into models is very important in order for these models to capture the semantic meaning better. The more resources and tools available for Uzbek, the higher the possibility to improve the results on NLP tasks.

The main aim of this study is to contribute to the NLP research community by tackling the challenge of topic classification for Uzbek language, specifically through a multi-label news categorization task. We introduced Uzbek topic classification dataset and assessed the performance of different models on it. These models span from traditional rule-based methods, like support vector machines (SVM) based on word and character n-grams, to more sophisticated deep learning models, including recurrent neural networks (RNN) and convolutional neural networks (CNN).

Literature review. Topic classification is a traditional challenge in the field of NLP. It has widely been deployed into different arenas such as aspect-oriented sentiment analysis[1], spam detection, news article categorization, and so forth. Recently, with the emergence of machine learning techniques, performances of the newer generation of topic classification have improved considerably. This simplicity in the traditional machine learning methods led to first use of this

task with Support Vector Machines(SVM) by [2], and Naive Bayes by [3]. Since then and in keeping with the explosion of text data and increase in the representational difficulty of the tasks, deep learning approaches have developed to such multiclass classification challenges.

Despite being classified as a low-resource language, there have been efforts to develop NLP resources and models for Uzbek. Significant contributions include the creation of sentiment analysis datasets [4-5], semantic evaluation datasets [6-7], and stop word datasets (Madatov et al., 2022). Additionally, NLP tools such as part-of-speech taggers [8], stemmers, and lemmatizes [9] have been developed to support Uzbek text processing. However, more work is required to further enhance the performance of NLP models on Uzbek language texts. Additionally, recent work by [10] introduces a comprehensive dataset for Uzbek language aspect-based sentiment analysis task, further advancing the development of NLP resources for Uzbek language. This paper highlights the growing focus on addressing the challenges of low-resource language processing.

Research Methodology. Topic classification requires a dataset that needs to be labeled and used for training and testing of the model. In this research, text data was collected from 7 different Uzbek news websites and press portals, which are news and press releases. Such news websites have been chosen with the aim of making the categories more varied: politics, sport, entertainment, technology, and so on. The data is collected through web scraping tools using the Scrapy framework for Python with BeautifulSoup, keeping information like source link, category name, title, and main content while doing the scraping. Pre-processing was done by categorizing every article into a particular one. We got a numerous and wide-ranging corpus for topic classification. The following table summarizes the sources, the number of articles retrieved from each source, and additional information describing the size of the dataset.

Category	Number of scraped links	Number of words
Gov. Law	33,089	27,000,100
Healthcare	5,086	1,300,000
Social news	54,018	13,900,000
Automobile	6,044	900,000

Table 1. Information about the corpus

In the experiments on the newly created dataset, we randomly split the data into a 5:3:2 ratio for training, validation, and testing. We have taken great care that each split would have an equal distribution of article categories. Several experiments have been conducted in this study to evaluate various models on Uzbek topic classification task. The models that were used in experiments are Logistic Regression with word n-grams, Logistic Regression with character n-grams, Logistic Regression with word+character n-grams, Recurrent Neural Network, Recurrent neural network without pretrained word embeddings for the experiments. Specifically, a bidirectional GRU with 100 hidden states was employed. The output of the hidden layer is a combination of the average and max pooling of the hidden states. Each model was trained on the training dataset, fine-tuned using the validation dataset, and its performance was evaluated on the test dataset. The rule-based models were used as baselines to benchmark the performance of the neural network models. The RNN and CNN models were applied to examine the capability of recurrent and convolutional neural networks in capturing sequence information and the semantic representation of Uzbek text data.

Analysis and results. In this section, we discuss the results of our experiments with various models explored for the task of topic classification on Uzbek language dataset. The performances of models are evaluated by using several metrics: accuracy, F1-score, and precision. After that, the F1-scores of each category in the dataset are summarized along with the average score for each model in Table 2.

ML&DL model names	F1-score	Law	Healthcare	Social news	Automobile
Logistic Regression with word n-grams	0.736	0.76	0.7	0.623	0.8
Logistic Regression with character n-grams	0.725	0.769	0.71	0.6	0.81
Logistic Regression with word+character n-grams	0.756	0.73	0.72	0.65	0.83
Recurrent Neural Network	0.79	0.83	0.8	0.66	0.89

Table 2 presents the evaluation results for topic classification across all models. The F1 scores for each model and category, as well as their mean values, are reported. The best scores, both overall and within each category, are highlighted for clarity.

From the model performances, it would seem that logistic regression models perform best when the model uses both word and character level n-grams by concatenating their TF-IDF matrices. Among the neural network models, such as RNN, which outperform rule-based models, their performance is improved further with infusion of language-specific knowledge in the form of pre-trained word-embedding vectors to achieve an F1-score of 0.79. Our experimental results prove that deep learning models perform well on topic classification tasks for Uzbek language.

Conclusion/Recommendations. In this paper, we try to approach text classification tasks for low-resource Uzbek. The result of our work constitutes a contribution to studies with a new dataset containing with more than 43 million words, spanning over 4 categories that were collected from 5 different news and press websites. The dataset was preprocessed by removing all unwanted data, like duplicates, references to images, emojis, and URLs, and transliterated from Cyrillic to Latin. We have conducted a performance comparison between rule-based models, deep learning models, multilingual transformer-based language, and monolingual transformer-based language models in our experiments. In this paper, we have tried to show that deep learning models can perform well in accomplishing the text classification task for Uzbek Language. In our future work, we would like to enhance the performance of the models by fine-tuning on a more extensive dataset and also extend the study to other NLP tasks such as Sentiment Analysis, Named Entity Recognition, and Machine Translation.

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